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EVALUATING THE INFLUENCE OF BUILDING SPATIAL LAYOUT ON OVERHANG PROJECTION FACTOR IN THE TEMPERATE DRY CLIMATE OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

A shading device is part of an external opening that shields the interior space of a building from direct sunlight and increases daylight, privacy, or view to the outside. The overhang projection factor (PF) is defined by ASHRAE 90.1(2016) as the ratio of the horizontal depth of the external shading projection divided by the sum of the height of the fenestration and the distance from the top of the fenestration to the bottom of the farthest point of the external shading projection, in consistent units. Scholars vary on the compromise values of PF for optimum Passive Indoor Thermal and Visual Comfort (PITVC) in buildings. For instance, a researcher has recommended a value of 0.55 and another has suggested a value of 0.5 for optimum PITVC, while a different approach was used as half of the window height for optimum PITVC. However, the effects of building spatial layout on the overhang projection factor have not been taken into consideration. This research aims to evaluate the influence of building spatial layout on overhang projection factor in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria. It was achieved by evaluating the range of values of projection factors in single-banked, double-banked, and open-planned office buildings to determine the difference in daylight autonomy (DA), useful daylight illuminance ($UDI_{100-3000}$), spatial daylight autonomy (sDA), operative temperature (OT) and relative humidity (RH) among them. Data was collected from simulation of the prototype single-banked, double-banked, and open-planned office buildings, using Google Sketch-Up 2017 and open-studio simulation tool which were done on the hypothetical sites devoid of surrounding buildings and trees, in Abuja, Zaria, and Jalingo. Data generated were then analysed using MANOVA, bar charts, column charts, graphs, and tables with a significance threshold of 0.05. The findings revealed that the best overhang projection factors are 0.35 and 0.6 for visual and thermal comfort in single-banked office buildings, 0.45/0.4 and 0.6 for double-banked, and 0.4 and 0.5 for open-planned office buildings respectively. When the values of daylight metrics and thermal comfort indicators were ranked together, 0.5 was found to be the most compromised value for single-banked, 0.5 for double-banked, and 0.45 for open-planned office buildings. One-way MANOVA was used and a statistically significant difference was obtained, $F(20, 116) = 2.487, p < .001$; Pillai's $\Lambda = 1.200$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.300$ for single-banked, $F(15, 222) = 5.479, p < .000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = .811$,

partial $\eta^2 = .270$ for double-banked and $F(15, 750) = 2.945, p = .000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = .944$, partial $\eta^2 = .315$ for open-planned office buildings. This study implies that the three (3) building spatial layouts must have different frameworks to achieve PITVC in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Keywords: Building spatial layout, Overhang projection factor, Shading, Thermal comfort, Visual comfort.

1.0 Introduction

Despite the numerous benefits of day-lighting and natural ventilation in buildings, they brought about great challenges to the building occupants such as thermal discomfort and glare especially in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria. Consequently, a well-designed fixed external shading system is recommended which can respond to changing environmental conditions, balance daylight and shade, control solar penetration, minimize solar heat gain, reduce glare, provide a view, and reinforce a comfortable indoor environment throughout the year while maintaining the aesthetic appeal of the Building (Shreejika, 2016). External shading devices can be utilized to block the solar radiation before it reaches the indoor environment, and are hence more effective than internal shading devices. There are generally three types of external shading devices in a building which are: vertical; horizontal; and egg crate shading devices. Many researchers have used more horizontal shading devices than the contrary, for it improves visual comfort (Al-Tamimi & Fadzil, 2011). However, one issue in question is the use of the overhang projection factor for a well-designed horizontal shading device to function appropriately. ASHRAE 90.1(2016) has defined the overhang projection factor (PF) as *the ratio of the horizontal depth (A) of the external shading projection divided by the sum of the height of the fenestration and the distance from the top of the fenestration to the bottom of the farthest point of the eternal shading projection (B), in consistent units, as shown in figure 1.1. The projection factor ranges between 0 and 1 value.*

Figure 1.1. Overhang projection factor

So many conflicting values of the optimum overhang projection factors were recommended by different researchers. For example, ASHRAE standard 90.1 (2016) recommended 0.5 value, Hien and Istiadji (2003), discovered 0.55 as the most effective for passive indoor comfort, while Yazhari, Nasrollahi, Mahdavinejad, (2018), recommended a ratio of 1:1.5 (window heights to overhang projection factor). However, they have not considered the effects of building spatial layout on the overhang projection factor. This study aims to evaluate the influence of building spatial layout on overhang projection factor in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria. It was done by using a range of values of overhang projection factors in single-banked, double-banked, and open-planned office building prototypes to determine the differences in the daylight autonomy (DA), useful daylight illuminance (UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀), spatial daylight autonomy (sDA), operative temperature (OT) and relative humidity (RH). These brought about the following hypothesis: The null hypothesis (H₀) states that the mean effects of PITVC are significantly the same for all the values of projection factors in the three different types of building spatial layout, while the alternative hypothesis (H₁) states that, the mean effects of PITVC is significantly different for at least one projection factor in single-banked, double-banked, and open planned office buildings.

Mardaljevic (2006) has noted that the provision of adequate daylighting and natural ventilation in buildings depends largely on the nature of the climate. Most climate classifications that are based on human comfort have their origin in Atkinson's (1953) climate classification (Koenigsberger, Ingersoll, Mayhew & Szokolay, 2013) as shown in Table 1.1a and b.

Table 1. 1a. Different types of climate classifications in Nigeria

S/No.	Climate title	Climate Zones	Factors used	Objective
1	Köppen classification in (Djamila & Yong 2016) (Nigeria)	Tropical wet climate, Tropical wet and dry climate, Hot-Semiarid Climate.	Air, temperature, and precipitation.	Vegetation (According to Olgyay (1963), the "classifications are not directly applicable to housing". This can be connected to the absence of humidity)
2	Miller's Climate Classification (1965) in (Ayoade, J.O. (2004) (world)	Hot climate, Warm climate, Cool temperate climate, Cold temperate climate, Arctic climate, Desert Climate, and Mountain climate.	Temperature and precipitation.	Vegetation

3	Thornthwaites' climate classification (1948) in (Ayoade, J.O. (2004). (world)	Perhumid, Humid1, Humid2, Humid3, Humid, Moist humid, Dry humid, Semi-Arid, and Arid	Temperature and precipitation.	Evapotranspiration (Ecology, Agriculture water resources).
4	Atkinson, (1953) in Koenigsberger, Ingersoll, Mayhew & Szokolay (2013). (Nigeria)	Warm Humid, Hot-dry Desert, Composite.	Temperature and humidity.	Thermal comfort
5	Koenigsberger (1974) (world)	Warm humid, trade-wind, Hot-dry desert, hot-dry maritime, composite, Tropical upland climates.	Temperature and humidity.	Thermal comfort

Table 1. 1b. Different types of climate classifications in Nigeria

S/No.	Climate title	Climate Zones	Factors used	Objective
6	Komolafe & Agwal (1987) (Nigeria)	Hot-dry climate, Temperate dry, Hot-humid climate, Warm-humid climate,	temperature, rainfall and relative humidity	Thermal comfort
7	Olufowobi, (1988) in Nwalusi, Anierobi, Efobi & Nwokolo, (2015). (Nigeria)	Warm/hot humid, hot-dry, Intermediate (composite).	Rainfall and temperature	Thermal comfort
8	WMO/UNEP, (2001)	Semi-Arid, Dry sub-humid, moist sub-humid, Humid	Temperature and precipitation.	Climate Change
9	National Universities Commission Method (Nigeria)	Northern Zone Southern Zone Transitional Zone	air temperature, humidity, wind, and annual rainfall	Analysis of seasons. Mobolade and Pourvahidi (2020) concluded that, It is too simplistic and lacking in scientific conviction
10	Nick-Hollo in (Ogunsote & Prucnal-Ogunsote 2002) (world)	Hot dry climate, Hot humid (zone II), Hot humid (zone IIa), Cool dry (Zone II), Cool dry (Zone IIa), Warm humid climates.	Unspecific climatic elements.	Depends heavily on descriptions and imagery.

11	Ogunsote & Prucnal-Ogunsote (2002). (Nigeria)	coastal zone, Forest zone, transitional zone, savannah zone, highland zone semi-desert.	Air temperature, relative humidity, Rainfall and Sunshine.	Occupants' satisfaction.
12	Szokolay, (2008) (world)	Cold Climates, Temperate (Moderate) Climates, Hot-Dry Climate, Warm-Humid Climate,	Temperature, Humidity, and Radiation.	Thermal comfort
13	Mobolade and Pourvahidi (2020) (Nigeria)	Hot-dry climate, Hot-humid climate, Temperate dry, Temperate humid, Temperate dry with cool climate	temperature, relative humidity, mean radiant temperature and wind velocity.	Bioclimatic Approach

Source: Musa, (2022)

The study has adopted Mobolade and Pourvahidi's (2020) climate classification based on the fact that it factored temperature, relative humidity, mean radiant temperature, and wind velocity in its method of classification. It also considered the gradual transition from one climatic zone to another as shown in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2 Classification of the Nigerian climate Mobolade and Pourvahidi.

Source: Mobolade and Pourvahidi (2020).

2.0 Materials and Methods

To evaluate the PITVC, the study used an experimental research strategy through a simulation method and a quantitative research design utilizing an explorative design approach. The

iterative prototypes of single-banked, double-banked, and open-planned office buildings (Bank of Industry, Federal Secretariat, and Bayero University Senate Buildings, respectively) were chosen using a convenience non-probability sampling technique. The Prototypes were modeled using Google Sketch-Up 2017 and OpenStudio simulation tools from January to December 2023 on the hypothetical sites devoid of surrounding buildings and trees, in Jalingo, Minna, and Zaria, and their mean values were used. Six (6) sets of offices (48) were used for the simulation and data generated were then analysed using the MANOVA statistical tool with a significance value of 0.05, bar charts, column charts, graphs, and Tables to find out the effects of a mid-rise office building spatial layout on the passive PITVC in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

3.0 Findings and Discussion

The simulations of single-banked, double-banked, and open-planned office buildings, with R-value of 2.08 m²K/W, azimuth angle of 11.5⁰, a Shade offset value of 0.3, and WWR of 20%, were done and the results are presented in Table 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 respectively.

Table 3.1 Simulation results for the effects of projection factors on visual comfort of a mid-rise office building in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Projection factor	0.35	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.600
DA	80	79	79	79	78
UDI	80	81	81	81	82
SDA	95.57	95.5	95.5	95.5	95.36

It has been observed that as the values of the Projection factor increase the DA and sDA decrease while the UDI increases.

Table 3.2. Simulation results for the effects of projection factors on visual comfort of double-bank mid-rise office building in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Projection factor	0.35	0.400	0.450	0.500
DA	65	61	61	59
UDI	72	73	74	75
SDA	78.85	83.2	83	82.55

It was noted from Table 3.2 that, none of the five (5) conditions has met the benchmark as put forward by IES, (2012) and AEC, (2013). It has also been observed that as the values of the projection factor increase the DA and sDA decrease while the UDI increases.

Table 3.3. Simulation results for the effects of projection factors on visual comfort of Open-plan mid-rise office building in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Projection factor	0.35	0.400	0.450	0.500
DA	68	68	67	66
UDI	79	80	80	80
SDA	94.11	94.4	94	93.5

It was noted from Table 3.3 that, all five (5) conditions have met the benchmark as put forward by IES, (2012) and AEC, (2013). The rank and percentile was used and the most compromised values for single-banked, double-banked, and open-planned for visual comfort were found to be 0.35, 0.45/0.4, and 0.4 respectively. The results have also revealed that single-banked office buildings have the highest Daylight Autonomy and the percentage of annual daytime hours that a defined position on the earth is more than an agreed illumination level, followed by open-planned and then double-banked as indicated in Figure 3.1 to 3.3.

Figure 3.1. Comparison of the effects of spatial layout on overhang projection factor for DA

Figure 3.2. Comparison of the effects of spatial layout on overhang projection factor for UDI

Figure 3.3. Comparison of the effects of spatial layout on overhang projection factor for sDA
 The simulation was done for the effects of overhang projection factors on operative temperature and relative humidity and the results revealed that the best projection factors for minimum operative temperature and maximum relative humidity for single-banked, double-banked, and open-planned are 0.6, 0.6, and 0.5 respectively. The values of daylight metrics and thermal comfort indicators were ranked together as indicated in table 3.4 to 3.6, 0.5 was found to be the most compromised value for single-banked, 0.5 for the double-banked, and 0.45 for the open-planned office buildings.

Table 3.4. Ranking of the projection factor for PITVC in single-banked office buildings

Projection factors	DA	UDI	sDA	Daylight Comfort	Thermal Comfort	PITVC	Remark
0.35	1 st	3 rd	1 st	1 st	4 th	4 th	0.5/0.6 are the most appropriate P.F for PITVC, in single-banked office buildings.
0.45	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	3 rd	3 rd	
0.5	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	1 st	
0.6	3 rd	1 st	3 rd	3 rd	1 st	1 st	

Table 3.5. Ranking of the projection factor for PITVC in double-banked office buildings

Projection factors	DA	UDI	sDA	Daylight Comfort	Thermal Comfort	PITVC	Remark
0.35	1 st	3 rd	1 st	1 st	4 th	4 th	0.5 is the most appropriate P.F for PITVC in double-banked office buildings.
0.45	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	3 rd	3 rd	
0.5	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	1 st	
0.6	3 rd	1 st	3 rd	3 rd	1 st	1 st	

Table 3.6. Ranking of the projection factor for PITVC in open-planned office buildings

Projection factors	DA	UDI	sDA	Daylight Comfort	Thermal Comfort	PITVC	Remark
0.35	1 st	3 rd	1 st	2 nd	4 th	4 th	0.45 is the most appropriate P.F for PITVC in open-planned office buildings.
0.4	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	1 st	3 rd	2 nd	
0.45	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	1 st	
0.5	3 rd	1 st	3 rd	4 th	1 st	3 rd	

The results have explained the findings of ASHRAE standard 90.1 (2016) and Hien and Istiadji (2003), which recommended 0.5 and 0.55 respectively.

3.1 Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: The null hypothesis states that the mean effects of PITVC are significantly the same for all the values of projection factors in the three different types of building spatial layout, while the alternative hypothesis (H₁) states that, the mean effects of PITVC are significantly different for at least one projection factor in single-banked, double-banked, and open planned office buildings.

The data were examined for skewness and kurtosis to test the hypothesis, and it was discovered that they fell within George and Mallery's (2010) acceptable range of values. The one-way MANOVA was used to test if the office building spatial layout differs from each other significantly in one or more overhead projection factors for PITVC in single-banked, double-banked, and open-planned offices and statistically significant differences were obtained, $F(20, 116) = 2.487, p < .001$; Pillai's $\Lambda = 1.200$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.300$ for single-banked, $F(15, 222) = 5.479, p < .000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = .811$, partial $\eta^2 = .270$ for double-banked and $F(15, 750) = 2.945, p = .000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = .944$, partial $\eta^2 = .315$ for open-planned office buildings.

A homogeneity for variance assumptions was tested for all five PITVC variables before conducting a series of tests between the subject effects. Based on a series of Levene's F tests, it was considered satisfactory. A Series of one-way ANOVAs on each of the five PITVC variables was conducted for each of the single-banked, double-banked, and open-planned office buildings as a follow-up test to the MANOVA. The results for the single-banked turned out to be statistically significant in all the DA ($F(4, 30) = 3.265; p < .025; partial \eta^2 = .303$), UDI ($F(4, 30) = 10.466; p < .0000; partial \eta^2 = .583$), SDA ($F(4, 30) = 4.500; p < .006; partial \eta^2 = .375$) and Operative temperature ($F(4, 30) = 2.843; p < .041; partial \eta^2 = .275$). Additionally, the outcomes for the double-banked buildings also show statistical significance in all the DA ($F(3, 76) = .863; p = .464; partial \eta^2 = .033$), UDI ($F(3, 76) = 5.274; p = .002; partial \eta^2 = .172$), sDA ($F(3, 76) = 7.35; p < .000; partial \eta^2 = .225$), Operative temperature ($F(3, 76) = 14.425; p < .000; partial \eta^2 = .363$) and Relative humidity ($F(3, 76) = 35.859; p < .000; partial \eta^2 = .589$). The open-planned office building has also turned out to be statistically significant in all the DA ($F(3, 252) = 2.568; p = .055; partial \eta^2 = .030$), UDI ($F(3, 252) = 16.852; p = .000; partial \eta^2 = .167$), sDA ($F(3, 252) = 5.238; p = .002; partial \eta^2 = .059$), Operative temperature ($F(3, 252) = 7.689; p < .000; partial \eta^2 = .084$), and Relative humidity ($F(3, 252) = 40.285; p < .000; partial \eta^2 = .324$).

4.0 Conclusion

The null hypothesis is therefore rejected and the study concludes that building spatial layout has a significant influence on the overhead projection factors for passive indoor thermal and visual comfort (PITVC) in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

5.0 Implication of the study

The study recommends that the three (3) building spatial layouts (single-banked, double-banked, and open-plan) must have different overhang projection factors for horizontal shading devices to achieve passive thermal and visual comfort in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

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